

Studies in Figured Tours of Knight in Two and Higher Dimensions

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Abstract

Tour of knight is over a millennium year old puzzle but 'Figured tour' of knight is a recent field of research. T. R. Dawson, an English chess problemist and the father of Fairy Chess, coined the term in 1940s. The name figured tour is appropriate for any numbered tour in which certain arithmetically related numbers are arranged in a geometrical pattern. Figured tours have been only looked into two-dimensional boards, mostly on 8x8 board. The author has constructed knight tour with square numbers in fiveleaper $\{3, 4\} + \{0, 5\}$ path and various other figured tours on 6x6 board and extended it in three and four dimensional space. Construction of figured tours is a mathematical recreation and can also be used in pedagogy of higher mathematics.

Key words: Knight, Tour, Higher dimensions.

Introduction: Knight's tour on chess board is an interesting ancient problem - over a millennium old. According to Dickins, [1] "The earliest known Knight's Tour dates from about 900 A.D. ..." Books related to recreational mathematics, namely, by Rouse Ball [2], Kraitchik [3], Pickover [4], Petkovic [5], Wells [6], Gardner [7] and by many others frequently cover knight's tour problem. It is basically a problem in graph theory — finding what is called a Hamiltonian path. Some great mathematical minds, such as, Raimond de Montmort, Abraham de Moivre, Jean-Jacques de Mairan, Vandermonde and Leonhard Euler have delved into the knight's tour problem. According to Jelliss, [8] "The name figured tour is appropriate for any numbered tour in which certain arithmetically related numbers are arranged in a geometrical pattern, since it combines in one concept both senses of the ambiguous term 'figure', which can mean either a numerical symbol or a geometrical shape. Tours in which all the entries participate in the arithmetical properties, for example arithmo-geometric tours in which the arithmetical properties derive from the geometrical structure such as symmetry, or magic tours which require calculation of rank and file totals, are not figured tours in this sense." Although tour of knight problem is over a millennium old, work on figured tour of knight began in 18th century. The term 'figured tour' was first used by the English chess problemist and 'father of Fairy Chess', T. R. Dawson in connection with his knight's tour showing the square numbers in closed, symmetrical circuits of knight moves in 1944. Perusal of literature reveals that 'figured tours' have been mostly looked into 8x8 board. What about 'figured tours' on 6x6 board? Can they be extended in 3 dimensions and even in 4 dimensions? The author plans to look into these questions.

1. Figured tours on 6x6 board: Like its conventional meaning, knight tour on a 6x6 board is consecutive knight moves where knight visits all the 36 cells without visiting any cell twice. First, knight's tours showing the square numbers in various formations are described and then knight's tours showing other numbers in formation are covered.

1A. Square numbers in formations: Figured tours with square numbers are comparatively easy to construct. It is because the number of intermediate cells between square numbers increases rapidly ; so there are fewer constraints as the tour progresses. Figure 1a by Jelliss [8] is

the only tour with the square numbers 1, 4, 9, 16, 25, 36 arranged in the order of magnitude in a row. There are only 11 tours (one closed and the rest open) with the square numbers in the order of magnitude as wazir moves. Wazir {0,1} is a fairy chess piece which moves only one step, along the rank or file, and the tour by Jelliss is one of them. Three more such tours are shown in Figure 1. If the 'order of magnitude' criteria is relaxed then there are 23 tours (3 closed and the rest open) with square numbers as wazir moves. Two such tours are shown in Figure 2. The square numbers in a knight sequence forming a closed chain of knight's moves is another interesting field. They are also called 'Dawsonian Tours' in the honour of T. R. Dawson who introduced them in 1932 and compiled 100 such symmetrical tours on 8x8 board over a span of 16 years. There are 12 closed tours on 6x6 board, none of them symmetric, and Figure 3 shows four of them.

1	4	9	16	25	36
10	17	26	3	8	15
5	2	7	14	35	24
18	11	20	27	32	29
21	6	13	30	23	34
12	19	22	33	28	31

a. (Jelliss)

8	1	4	25	36	15
3	24	9	16	5	26
10	7	2	35	14	17
23	34	21	6	27	30
20	11	32	29	18	13
33	22	19	12	31	28

b.

17	36	15	24	19	34
8	25	18	35	14	23
5	16	7	22	33	20
26	9	4	1	30	13
3	6	11	28	21	32
10	27	2	31	12	29

c.

36	25	28	17	14	23
27	16	35	24	29	18
4	9	26	15	22	13
1	34	3	8	19	30
10	5	32	21	12	7
33	2	11	6	31	20

d.

Fig.1. Knight tour with square numbers in the order of magnitude as wazir {0,1} moves.

5	36	25	16	27	2
18	9	4	1	24	15
35	6	17	26	3	28
10	19	8	31	14	23
7	34	21	12	29	32
20	11	30	33	22	13

a.

5	36	25	16	27	2
24	9	4	1	18	15
35	6	17	26	3	28
10	23	8	31	14	19
7	34	21	12	29	32
22	11	30	33	20	13

b.

Fig.2. Knight tour with square numbers, in a rectangle, as wazir {0,1} moves.

There are 72 open tours with the six square numbers in knight's paths. In few tours, polygons, none of them regular, can be constructed by joining the starting and ending cells. Figure 4 shows two interesting tours in which the polygons have smallest and largest areas, being 3 units and 7 units respectively. 'Non attacking queens' is another famous problem. It is to place 'n' queens on an n x n board so that none of them attack each other. There are 12 fundamental solutions for 8x8 board. If the square numbers are taken to represent 'queens' then Dawson and Jelliss have given solutions for 8x8 board. Now, let us come to 6x6 board. Can there be a knight tour on 6x6 board in which the square numbers representing queens are non-attacking? To answer this question, let us have a look at the 6x6 board with six non-attacking queens as shown in Figure 5.

This is the only fundamental solution for non-attacking queens on 6x6 board. In order to have the six square numbers in this formation, three of them have to be on black squares and the other three on white squares, being odd and even. Since the non-attacking queens are four on black and two on white squares, so there can't be a knight tour on 6x6 board in which the square numbers representing queens are non-attacking.

7	10	23	36	21	12
24	1	8	11	26	35
9	6	25	22	13	20
2	31	4	17	34	27
5	16	29	32	19	14
30	3	18	15	28	33

a.

17	6	19	28	15	8
26	29	16	7	20	35
5	18	27	36	9	14
30	25	4	13	34	21
3	12	23	32	1	10
24	31	2	11	22	33

b.

17	6	23	32	15	8
24	3	16	7	30	33
5	18	31	22	9	14
2	25	4	13	34	29
19	12	27	36	21	10
26	1	20	11	28	35

c.

17	8	19	28	15	6
26	29	16	7	20	35
9	18	27	36	5	14
30	25	4	13	34	21
3	10	23	32	1	12
24	31	2	11	22	33

d.

Fig.3. Knight tours with square numbers in a closed chain of knight moves.

17	6	19	28	15	8
26	29	16	7	20	35
5	18	27	36	9	14
30	25	4	13	34	21
1	12	23	32	3	10
24	31	2	11	22	33

a. Area of polygon = 3 units

21	10	27	12	15	8
28	3	22	9	26	13
23	20	11	14	7	16
2	29	4	25	32	35
19	24	31	34	17	6
30	1	18	5	36	33

b. Area of polygon = 7 units

Fig.4. Square numbers as knight's path forming polygons with smallest and largest area.

Monogram tours, that is, knight tours delineating letter shapes, have an aesthetic appeal. Four such tours depicting letters J, K, L and X are shown in Figure 6. Figure 7 shows closed tours with the square numbers at knight's move around the starting cell 1. Magic sum properties are not usually considered in figured tours but as a bonus, three rows are also summing up to magic constant 111 in the tour shown in Figure 7a.

	Q				
			Q		
					Q
Q					
		Q			
				Q	

6 Non-attacking queens

	1				
			4		
					9
16					
		36			
				25	

No such tour possible because of 4 black and 2 white cells

Fig.5. Non-attacking queens on 6x6 board

Fig.6. Monogram tours (knight tours delineating letter shapes).

Fig.7. Closed knight tour with square number at knight's move from starting cell 1.

Figure 8 shows knight tours with square numbers along the sides of parallelogram. Figure 8b has two rows summing up to magic constant 111. Figure 9 shows closed knight tours with square numbers in the corners. Figure 10 shows knight tours with square numbers in the 4x4 corners.

Fig.8. Knight tours with square numbers along the sides of parallelogram.

1	6	13	28	31	4
14	27	2	5	12	29
23	36	7	30	3	32
26	15	24	19	8	11
35	22	17	10	33	20
16	25	34	21	18	9

a.

9	14	31	28	3	16
30	21	10	15	32	27
13	8	29	2	17	4
22	1	20	11	26	33
7	12	35	24	5	18
36	23	6	19	34	25

b.

Fig.9. Closed knight tours with square numbers in the corners.

9	6	15	2	27	4
14	1	8	5	16	29
7	10	35	28	3	26
34	13	22	19	30	17
23	36	11	32	25	20
12	33	24	21	18	31

a.

9	34	15	2	7	4
14	1	8	5	16	27
35	10	33	26	3	6
32	13	22	19	28	17
23	36	11	30	25	20
12	31	24	21	18	29

b.

Fig.10. Knight tours with square numbers in the 4x4 corners.

Figure 11 shows knight tours with square numbers in the central squares. Figure 11b has 5 magic lines (4 columns and 1 row) as bonus. Figure 12 shows closed knight tours with powers of 2 at knight move from square 1. We have already seen squares in wazir {0,1} and knight {1,2} paths. In general, an {r,s}-leaper is a piece that moves (or leaps) from cell (x,y) to any of the cells (x±r, y±s) or (x±s, y±r). In fairy chess, there are three other leapers, namely, giraffe {1,4}, zebra {2,3} and antelope {3,4} that move alternately between white and black squares.

1	8	11	34	21	6
10	33	22	7	12	35
23	2	9	36	5	20
32	17	4	25	28	13
3	24	15	30	19	26
16	31	18	27	14	29

a.

21	2	11	32	23	4	93
12	33	22	3	10	31	111
1	20	9	16	5	24	75
34	13	36	25	30	27	165
19	8	15	28	17	6	93
14	35	18	7	26	29	129
101	111	111	111	111	121	

b.

Fig.11. Knight tours with square numbers in the central squares.

5	16	19	34	7	36
18	27	6	1	20	33
15	4	17	26	35	8
28	25	2	11	32	21
3	14	23	30	9	12
24	29	10	13	22	31

a.

7	16	25	34	5	36
18	27	6	1	24	33
15	8	17	26	35	4
28	19	2	11	32	23
9	14	21	30	3	12
20	29	10	13	22	31

b.

Fig.12. Closed knight tours with powers of 2 at knight move from square 1.

1	20	3	30	15	18
36	31	16	19	4	29
21	2	23	32	17	14
24	35	10	7	28	5
11	22	33	26	13	8
34	25	12	9	6	27

a. Area of polygon = 10 units

11	20	1	22	9	14
36	23	10	13	2	7
19	12	21	8	15	30
24	35	26	31	6	3
27	18	33	4	29	16
34	25	28	17	32	5

b. Area of polygon = 14 units

17	36	1	24	19	22
2	31	18	21	8	25
35	16	3	32	23	20
30	13	34	7	26	9
15	4	11	28	33	6
12	29	14	5	10	27

c.

31	18	1	22	9	20
16	23	32	19	2	7
33	30	17	8	21	10
24	15	26	11	6	3
29	34	13	4	27	36
14	25	28	35	12	5

d.

Fig.13. Knight tours with square numbers in giraffe {1,4} path.

The author has constructed over twenty tours with square numbers in giraffe paths and four examples are shown in Figure 13. The smallest polygon formed by the giraffe path has area of 10 units and the largest one is of 14 units. Readers may like to improve upon it. Jelliss [8] has constructed a closed giraffe path on 8x8 board but the author couldn't get one on 6x6 board. Probably, it doesn't exist. Readers are requested to prove or disprove the conjecture. The author has constructed 17 tours, 14 open and 3 closed, with square numbers in zebra paths and 4 tours are shown in Figure 14. The author couldn't get a closed zebra path. Readers are requested to look for its existence. Jelliss [8] jots, "Other tasks to be considered here are, for example, {3,4} or {2,5} or fiveleaper paths. Some of these look difficult, if not impossible." Here, Jelliss is talking about 8x8 board. The author has constructed a knight tour on 8x8 board with square numbers in antelope {3,4} path as shown in Figure 15a. The author couldn't get a closed knight tour or a closed antelope {3,4} path. Readers are requested to look for them. It is really difficult with {2,5} leaper. The nearest, the author could get is shown in Figure 15b where all square numbers except 49-64 are in {2,5} leaper path. Perhaps, knight tour with square numbers in {2,5} leaper path doesn't exist on 8x8 board. Readers are requested to prove or disprove this conjecture. The author couldn't get a knight tour with square numbers in fiveleaper {3,4}+{0,5} closed path and readers are requested to look into it. Knight tours with square numbers as antelope {3,4} paths or {2,5} leaper paths are not possible on 6x6 board. Readers can check that the board is just too small for them. However, knight tour with square numbers in fiveleaper {3,4}+{0,5} path is possible and the author could get only one tour as shown in Figure 16. Here, the symmetry of line diagram joining consecutive square numbers looks elegant.

1	12	25	6	3	30
24	7	2	31	26	5
11	32	13	4	29	36
8	23	10	27	16	19
33	14	21	18	35	28
22	9	34	15	20	17

a.

3	12	25	14	1	6
26	15	2	5	24	21
11	4	13	22	7	36
16	27	34	31	20	23
33	10	29	18	35	8
28	17	32	9	30	19

b.

3	14	25	22	1	12
26	23	2	13	32	21
7	4	15	24	11	36
16	27	6	33	20	31
5	8	29	18	35	10
28	17	34	9	30	19

c.

17	12	19	36	5	14
20	3	16	13	26	35
11	18	31	4	15	6
2	21	10	27	34	25
9	30	23	32	7	28
22	1	8	29	24	33

d.

Fig.14. Knight tours with square numbers in zebra {2,3} path.

47	52	23	4	45	36	21	6
24	3	46	35	22	5	10	37
53	48	51	44	11	34	7	20
50	25	2	57	32	19	38	9
1	54	49	12	43	8	33	18
26	13	56	61	58	31	42	39
55	60	15	28	63	40	17	30
14	27	62	59	16	29	64	41

a. antelope {3,4} path

43	48	45	28	41	26	23	52
46	29	42	49	22	51	40	25
1	44	47	62	27	24	53	60
30	63	16	21	50	61	8	39
17	2	31	64	35	10	59	54
32	15	20	11	56	7	38	9
3	18	13	34	5	36	55	58
14	33	4	19	12	57	6	37

b. {2,5} leaper path (nearest approach)

Fig.15. Knight tour with square numbers in (a) {3,4} and (b) {2,5} leaper path.

11	32	9	28	13	30
36	27	12	31	8	25
33	10	35	26	29	14
20	17	2	5	24	7
1	34	19	22	15	4
18	21	16	3	6	23

Fig.16. Knight tour with square numbers in fiveleaper {3,4} + {0,5} path.

1B. Other numbers in formations: Tours having numbers in arithmetic progression are also of interest. In general, it is more difficult to get figured tours with arithmetic progressions than the tours with square numbers because unlike latter, the number of intermediate cells is fixed. So the choice for subsequent moves gets restricted as the tour progresses. There are no tours with all the numbers along even diagonal in a multiple of 6. However, two such nearest approach tours are shown in Figure 17. There are no tours in arithmetic progression with common difference 6 along the even or odd diagonals. Two such nearest approach tours are shown in Figure 18. However, if the order of magnitude criterion is relaxed, odd diagonal in Figure 18b has all the numbers in arithmetic progression. Now let us come to tours with rows in arithmetic progression having common difference (CD) as 3 or 5 or 7. That is, tours with 1-4-7-10-13-16 (CD 3) or 1-6-11-16-21-26 (CD 5) or 1-8-15-22-29-36 (CD 7) along any row with any sequence. Jelliss [9] has shown that there is no tour with numbers in arithmetic progression along rows or columns “even if we drop the requirement for the numbers to be in order of magnitude.” However, two nearest approach tours are shown in Figure 19.

1	28	13	20	3	6
30	21	2	5	12	19
27	14	29	18	7	4
22	31	24	9	34	11
15	26	35	32	17	8
36	23	16	25	10	33

a.

15	28	13	20	17	6
30	21	16	5	12	19
27	14	29	18	7	4
22	31	24	9	34	11
1	26	35	32	3	8
36	23	2	25	10	33

b.

Fig.17. Knight tour with multiples of 6 along even diagonal (nearest approach).

1	12	15	6	3	22
14	7	2	23	16	5
11	28	13	4	21	24
8	31	10	19	34	17
27	36	29	32	25	20
30	9	26	35	18	33

a.

1	12	15	8	23	10
14	7	36	11	16	21
35	2	13	22	9	24
6	27	4	31	20	17
3	34	29	18	25	32
28	5	26	33	30	19

b.

Fig.18. Knight tour with common difference 6 along odd diagonal (nearest approach).

1	4	7	16	13	22
6	17	2	21	26	15
3	8	5	14	23	12
18	31	20	25	34	27
9	36	29	32	11	24
30	19	10	35	28	33

a.

14	21	12	9	16	23
1	8	15	22	29	10
20	13	2	11	24	17
7	34	19	28	3	30
36	27	32	5	18	25
33	6	35	26	31	4

b.

Fig.19. Knight tour with a row in arithmetic progression (nearest approach).

The numbers of the form $n(n+1)/2$, that is, 1,3,6,10,15,21,28,36,... are called triangular numbers. Figure 20 shows knight tour with triangular numbers forming trapezium and in a compact formation. Figure 21 shows triangular numbers in triangular and octagonal formation. All the triangular numbers are equidistant from the centre of the 6 x 6 board in Figure 21b. We subtract 1 from 1,3,7,13,21,31 to get 0,2,6,12,20,30 which are called 'metasquare numbers' or 'Double triangle numbers' of form $n(n+1)$. Figure 22 shows two tours with 'metasquare numbers' along long diagonals. The numbers of the form $n(3n-1)/2$, that is, 1,5,12,22,35,... are called pentagonal numbers. Figure 23 shows tours with pentagonal numbers forming smallest and largest pentagons having 7 units and 20.5 units of area respectively.

9	20	27	24	11	22
26	3	10	21	28	1
19	8	25	2	23	12
4	33	6	15	36	29
7	18	31	34	13	16
32	5	14	17	30	35

a. Isoceles trapezium

7	2	5	12	9	20
4	13	8	19	26	11
1	6	3	10	21	36
14	31	34	25	18	27
33	24	29	16	35	22
30	15	32	23	28	17

b. Isoceles trapezium

9	32	35	2	11	16
34	3	10	15	36	1
31	8	33	12	17	14
4	21	6	19	28	25
7	30	23	26	13	18
22	5	20	29	24	27

c. Right angled trapezium

9	20	29	4	11	2
30	5	10	1	36	27
19	8	21	28	3	12
22	31	6	15	26	35
7	18	33	24	13	16
32	23	14	17	34	25

d. Compact formation

Fig.20. Knight tour with triangular numbers forming trapezium and in a compact formation.

9	24	27	2	11	18
26	3	10	17	28	1
23	8	25	12	19	16
4	33	6	15	36	29
7	22	31	34	13	20
32	5	14	21	30	35

a. Triangular formation

13	16	1	36	7	18
24	29	14	17	2	35
15	12	23	8	19	6
28	25	30	5	34	3
11	22	27	32	9	20
26	31	10	21	4	33

b. Octagonal formation

Fig.21. Triangular numbers in triangular and octagonal formation.

2	19	22	11	8	33
23	12	1	32	21	10
18	3	20	9	34	7
13	24	15	0	31	28
4	17	26	29	6	35
25	14	5	16	27	30

a.

6	19	22	11	8	33
21	12	7	32	23	10
18	5	20	9	34	1
13	28	15	0	31	24
4	17	26	29	2	35
27	14	3	16	25	30

b.

Fig.22. Knight tour with 'Metasquare numbers' along long diagonals.

9	20	35	28	11	14
36	29	10	13	22	27
19	8	21	34	15	12
30	1	32	5	26	23
7	18	3	24	33	16
2	31	6	17	4	25

a. Area of pentagon = 7 units

1	16	19	30	5	10
18	31	4	9	20	29
15	2	17	6	11	8
32	25	34	3	28	21
35	14	23	26	7	12
24	33	36	13	22	27

b. Area of pentagon = 20.5 units

Fig.23. Knight tour with pentagonal numbers forming smallest and largest pentagons.

Numbers in the sequence 1, 2, 3, 5, 8, 13, 21, 34 ... are called Fibonacci numbers, named after the 12th century Italian mathematician Leonardo of Pisa, later known as Fibonacci. Figure 24 shows tours with Fibonacci numbers forming smallest and largest polygons having 5 units and 12 units of area respectively. It is obvious from the figures that a larger polygon is not possible; however, readers may look for a smaller polygon. Numbers in the sequence 2, 1, 3, 4, 7, 11, 18, 29 ... are called Lucas numbers, named after the 19th century French mathematician Edouard Lucas. Figure 25 shows tours with Lucas numbers forming smallest and largest polygon having 5 units and 19 units of area respectively. Readers may look to improve upon them. Prime numbers have been fascinating humankind for over 2000 years. Figure 26 shows odd primes in rectangle and trapezium formation. It is interesting to note that Figure 26b has five rows adding to 113. 'Domination by queen' is another classic problem and Figure 27 shows all the primes being dominated by queen at cell 13 and 11 respectively. As a bonus, Figure 27b has two magic rows too.

13	16	33	22	7	4
34	21	14	5	32	23
15	12	17	8	3	6
28	35	20	1	24	31
11	18	29	26	9	2
36	27	10	19	30	25

a. Area of polygon = 5 units

23	14	35	12	25	20
36	11	24	21	34	29
15	22	13	28	19	26
10	5	8	1	30	33
7	16	3	32	27	18
4	9	6	17	2	31

b. Area of polygon = 5 units

3	28	31	18	5	8
32	19	4	7	30	17
27	2	29	16	9	6
20	33	22	25	12	15
1	26	35	14	23	10
34	21	24	11	36	13

c. Area of polygon = 23 units

3	26	29	10	5	8
28	17	4	7	30	11
25	2	27	18	9	6
16	35	20	23	12	31
1	24	33	14	19	22
34	15	36	21	32	13

d. Area of polygon = 23 units

Fig. 24. Knight tour with Fibonacci numbers forming smallest and largest polygons.

5	36	7	10	19	2
8	11	4	1	30	17
35	6	9	18	3	20
12	25	22	31	16	29
23	34	27	14	21	32
26	13	24	33	28	15

a. Area of polygon = 5 units

7	4	21	32	15	2
22	13	6	3	20	31
5	8	33	14	1	16
12	23	10	19	30	27
9	34	25	28	17	36
24	11	18	35	26	29

b. Area of polygon = 19 units

Fig. 25. Knight tour with Lucas numbers forming smallest and largest polygon.

27	6	11	2	21	4
10	19	28	5	12	1
7	26	9	20	3	22
32	29	18	15	36	13
25	8	31	34	23	16
30	33	24	17	14	35

a.

1	36	21	14	11	30	113
20	15	2	29	22	13	101
35	6	19	12	31	10	113
18	3	16	23	28	25	113
7	34	5	26	9	32	113
4	17	8	33	24	27	113

b.

3	10	5	22	1	12
36	23	2	11	6	21
9	4	7	20	13	30
24	35	26	31	16	19
27	8	33	18	29	14
34	25	28	15	32	17

c.

7	10	5	22	1	12
36	23	8	11	4	21
9	6	17	30	13	2
24	35	26	3	20	31
27	16	33	18	29	14
34	25	28	15	32	19

d.

Fig. 26. Odd primes in (a, b) rectangle and in (c, d) trapezium.

17	22	15	10	7	24
14	11	18	23	36	9
21	16	13	8	25	6
12	31	2	19	28	35
3	20	33	30	5	26
32	1	4	27	34	29

a.

7	10	21	14	31	28	111
20	13	8	29	22	15	107
9	6	11	32	27	30	115
12	19	2	23	16	33	105
5	24	35	18	3	26	111
36	1	4	25	34	17	117

b.

Fig. 27. Queen at cell 13 in (a) and at cell 11 in (b) dominating all the primes.

2. Figured tours in three dimensions: For almost a millennium, knight's tour was confined to two-dimensional board and was extended into three dimensions in 18th century. A.T. Vandermonde [10], a mathematician, musician and chemist, was the first to construct a three-dimensional knight's tour, in a 4×4×4 cube, published in 1771. Other 3D examples have been provided by Schubert [11], Gibbins [12], Stewart [13], Jelliss [14], Petkovic [15] and DeMaio [16]. More recently, Awani Kumar [17] [18] [19] [20], looked into the possibilities of knight's tours in cubes and cuboids, having magic properties. In three dimensions, the knight is assumed to move in its usual fashion in each of the three mutually perpendicular planes through the cell it initially occupies. If the three coordinate directions are x, y, z then the three planes can be represented by the pairs of coordinates xy, xz, yz . Thus the mobility of the knight is multiplied three-fold; on a two-dimensional board the knight has a choice of up to 8 cells to which it can move, but in three dimensions it can have as many as 24 cells to move. However, on small boards, or near the edges of larger boards, the number of moves will of course be less than this maximum, since blocked by the board edges or faces. The knight cannot move at all in a 2×2×2 cube, or from the central cell of a 3×3×3 cube. So the smallest cubical board on which the knight is mobile on every cell is the 4×4×4 cube and the author plans to look for 'Figured tours' in it. Figure 28 shows the 12 possible moves of a knight from an inner cell of a 4×4×4 cube.

Fig. 28. Possible knight's move in 4x4x4 cube.

Readers can visualize this 3D board as a stack of four 2D boards, one above the other, lettered in alphabetical order A to D. As in the 2D case the cubical cells (or their floors) can be coloured alternately light and dark so that a knight at a light cell can only jump to a dark cell and vice versa. This remains true in higher dimensions too. Figure 29a and Figure 29b show square numbers in the corner cells and in the central cells of the cube, respectively.

1	42	29	4	62	27	2	13	21	34	5	46	64	47	22	49
30	17	38	41	15	12	53	50	6	43	20	33	61	24	57	54
39	28	3	32	26	51	14	11	63	18	45	8	56	35	48	23
16	31	40	9	59	10	37	52	44	7	58	19	25	60	55	36

a.

33	2	11	54	40	59	62	3	31	18	55	26	22	41	8	61
10	53	48	27	47	4	9	58	24	49	36	19	5	60	23	42
39	34	63	12	32	1	16	43	17	64	25	56	30	21	44	7
52	13	38	57	15	46	51	28	50	35	14	37	45	6	29	20

b.

Fig. 29. Knight tour with square numbers in (a) corner cells and (b) central cells.

Figure 30a and Figure 30b show cubic numbers and square numbers in the corner cells and in the central cells of the cube, respectively. Figure 31a and Figure 31b show square numbers in a circular formation on the surface and inside the cube, respectively. Figure 32a and Figure 32b show square numbers in a closed chain of knight moves in square and diamond quarte and in Beverley quarte, respectively. It is just to remind the readers that William Beverley was the first person to construct a magic knight tour on 8x8 board using what is now known as 'beverley quarte', in 1848.

1	12	39	8	18	37	6	33	55	50	11	38	36	17	52	49
22	45	28	13	63	32	23	48	2	59	62	29	53	24	5	58
19	14	9	40	54	41	34	7	15	44	51	10	56	35	16	43
64	31	20	27	21	46	61	30	60	3	26	47	25	42	57	4

a.

34	37	26	47	9	14	55	18	30	51	38	3	39	2	13	52
31	46	35	24	54	1	8	15	7	36	25	50	10	53	40	19
6	33	48	17	61	64	27	56	32	49	4	43	29	58	63	12
45	22	5	42	28	57	60	23	21	44	41	16	62	11	20	59

b.

Fig. 30. Knight tour with square numbers and cubic numbers in the (a) corner cells and (b) central cells.

39	36	1	56
16	63	48	25
49	58	15	64
52	9	4	47

22	57	40	37
53	8	5	62
44	23	32	59
17	60	43	24

35	38	31	2
50	11	34	55
33	14	3	26
10	51	46	61

30	21	6	41
7	54	29	20
18	27	42	13
45	12	19	28

a.

7	44	13	2
54	3	6	33
45	8	55	12
26	53	28	5

60	1	36	21
49	52	61	64
16	35	48	9
47	4	25	32

39	20	57	14
46	43	40	11
59	56	15	34
42	27	62	29

50	37	22	19
41	18	63	30
38	51	58	23
17	24	31	10

b.

Fig. 31. Knight tour with square numbers in a circle (a) on the surface and (b) inside the cube.

5	24	29	62
32	61	8	19
59	6	33	30
34	31	48	7

56	1	22	27
35	40	55	16
4	15	58	63
47	54	9	18

23	28	57	64
50	25	52	41
45	60	49	20
36	51	46	53

12	39	2	21
3	42	13	26
38	11	44	17
43	14	37	10

a.

1	12	31	18
22	19	4	27
11	44	21	16
20	9	26	5

30	37	2	59
3	42	53	6
54	15	60	35
23	34	41	8

13	62	49	28
64	45	32	17
61	36	63	50
10	43	46	25

38	29	56	51
55	52	39	58
14	57	48	7
47	24	33	40

b.

Fig. 32. Square numbers in a closed chain of knight moves in (a) square and diamond, (b) Beverley quartet.

Figure 33 shows knight tour with square numbers at the corners of a truncated pyramid. Figure 34 shows knight tour with square numbers at the corners of a three-dimensional trapezoid (or trapezoidal prism). Figure 35 shows closed knight tour with square numbers in zebra {2,3} path. Figure 36 shows knight tour with square numbers in closed zebra {2,3} path. Figure 37 shows closed tour of knight with powers of 2 at knight move from cell 1.

1	46	53	4
28	59	8	55
41	54	3	60
16	43	58	9

34	19	2	51
13	50	35	38
18	45	26	5
27	12	17	44

29	52	47	20
62	39	56	7
15	42	61	48
40	63	10	57

14	21	30	37
33	64	25	22
24	49	36	31
11	32	23	6

Fig. 33. Knight tour with square numbers at the corners of a truncated pyramid.

1	30	41	64
10	37	56	59
35	58	21	8
18	9	36	57

44	5	20	31
19	60	51	6
46	27	40	63
11	48	17	14

29	26	39	54
2	55	42	13
43	38	33	22
34	23	12	7

4	53	32	25
45	24	3	50
28	61	52	15
47	16	49	62

Fig. 34. Knight tour with square numbers as three-dimensional trapezoid (or trapezoidal prism).

25	52	19	2
44	59	56	51
57	26	47	36
32	35	58	55

12	1	24	17
31	34	43	62
10	23	20	27
41	60	39	4

45	18	53	64
42	63	50	3
49	46	37	54
38	33	48	61

30	13	16	7
11	6	29	14
22	15	8	5
9	40	21	28

Fig. 35. Closed Knight tour with square numbers in zebra {2,3} path in 4x4x4 cube.

1	44	17	10
14	11	32	47
45	2	13	36
12	31	46	33

16	41	6	61
51	60	15	40
58	37	50	9
29	34	59	22

7	18	43	64
28	63	48	19
49	8	3	62
52	21	30	35

42	5	56	25
57	24	39	54
4	55	26	23
27	38	53	20

Fig. 36. Knight tour with square numbers in closed zebra {2,3} path in 4x4x4 cube.

1	30	15	46
24	45	4	29
13	2	31	26
54	25	12	3

14	47	64	37
63	52	7	44
32	39	60	51
11	42	55	28

23	16	49	20
8	41	62	27
61	48	5	38
34	53	10	43

58	21	6	17
33	18	57	36
22	59	50	19
9	40	35	56

Fig. 37. Closed tour of knight with powers of 2 at knight move from starting cell 1.

Figure 38 shows tours of knight with cell 1 equidistant from multiples of (a) 6, (b) 8, (c) 10, and (d) 12, respectively. Here Figure 38a is an open tour. Readers are requested to improve upon it to get a closed knight tour. There are 4 space diagonals in a cube. Figure 39 shows two tours with square numbers along the space diagonals.

41	32	3	44
2	39	62	33
25	56	43	38
22	37	12	53

24	57	50	29
63	28	1	52
42	35	58	55
11	54	27	36

31	40	47	16
48	61	4	45
23	46	49	34
26	21	60	13

64	17	30	51
5	8	59	18
10	19	6	15
7	14	9	20

a.

39	18	41	2
62	31	38	19
37	40	61	30
46	63	58	13

42	1	44	15
45	50	59	32
24	29	56	3
57	12	53	20

17	28	35	8
36	7	54	49
55	64	23	14
52	47	60	11

34	43	16	27
51	48	33	6
22	5	26	9
25	10	21	4

b.

14	1	6	33
3	48	15	10
30	17	50	5
49	4	47	16

7	32	13	20
62	37	56	59
27	64	29	18
38	61	36	55

2	21	40	9
39	60	51	34
42	31	22	11
23	52	43	46

41	8	57	12
24	53	44	19
63	28	25	58
26	45	54	35

c.

34	17	2	41
3	52	49	18
24	35	40	5
51	4	7	62

1	42	39	14
50	57	64	61
33	60	25	22
8	63	54	19

16	37	48	21
45	30	53	58
36	23	28	47
29	46	31	6

43	12	15	38
10	59	44	13
27	56	11	20
32	9	26	55

d.

Fig.38. Knight tour with multiples of (a) 6, (b) 8, (c) 10, and (d) 12 at knight move from starting cell 1.

1	6	37	60
40	59	52	5
43	62	23	38
64	39	14	53

48	61	22	3
27	4	41	34
18	49	44	57
13	58	17	50

7	2	47	56
42	55	36	51
63	46	9	24
28	15	54	35

32	21	10	25
11	26	33	30
8	31	20	45
19	12	29	16

a.

1	42	31	54
52	29	12	33
13	32	53	30
18	11	14	25

38	35	44	5
19	4	61	28
2	43	36	45
51	24	17	58

41	8	55	34
62	49	20	59
37	56	9	26
10	15	48	23

64	39	6	27
3	60	63	22
40	7	46	57
47	50	21	16

b.

Fig.39. Knight tour with square numbers along space diagonals in 4x4x4 cube.

Figure 27 showed 'domination by queen' in two dimensions. Figure 40 shows possible queen's move in three dimensions and Figure 41 shows queen at cell 5 dominating all the primes in 4x4x4 cube.

•	•	•	
•	•	•	
•	•	•	

	•		•
•	•	•	
•	Q	•	•
•	•	•	

•	•	•	
•	•	•	
•	•	•	

	•		•
	•		•

Fig. 40. Possible queen's move in 4x4x4 cube (shown as dots).

1	14	33	20
18	53	58	15
59	48	19	6
52	17	62	27

32	47	40	7
51	44	63	4
2	5	60	41
61	54	3	16

39	30	57	12
64	13	34	21
31	56	49	28
50	43	26	55

46	37	8	23
9	22	45	36
38	29	24	11
25	10	35	42

Fig. 41. Queen (at cell 5) dominating all the primes in 4x4x4 cube.

Monogram tours, that is, knight tours delineating letter shapes, have an aesthetic appeal. Fourteen such tours depicting letters C, D, J, L, T and X are shown in Figure 42. Letter O has already been shown in Figure 31.

9	4	1	38
16	37	32	41
25	40	13	2
36	49	64	31

22	55	12	3
57	50	63	30
8	61	56	39
17	58	33	48

5	10	23	28
44	15	42	47
35	24	27	14
26	43	46	19

54	21	6	11
7	62	53	20
60	51	34	29
45	18	59	52

a. C-shape

2	41	10	19
11	50	45	58
40	3	18	53
17	52	47	44

9	4	1	60
16	59	30	43
25	54	37	20
36	49	64	57

12	55	38	33
39	42	63	56
8	51	46	61
15	62	7	48

5	32	23	28
24	29	6	31
13	22	27	34
26	35	14	21

b. C-shape

1	36	39	22
4	41	64	11
9	38	49	40
16	25	10	31

46	51	48	7
63	28	61	32
50	35	8	57
3	62	15	12

5	34	21	52
2	37	44	23
45	42	53	30
26	17	24	43

20	47	6	33
27	60	19	56
54	29	58	13
59	14	55	18

c. D-shape

10	55	50	23
63	44	3	54
2	27	46	59
29	62	17	26

1	36	41	48
4	53	64	39
9	60	49	24
16	25	8	61

42	51	22	37
11	56	43	52
30	45	58	47
57	28	31	18

5	20	35	40
34	13	32	19
15	6	21	38
12	33	14	7

d. D-shape

5	48	1	10
64	11	4	47
49	46	9	12
36	25	16	43

2	51	30	55
37	58	63	40
52	33	38	61
17	42	35	26

29	22	3	60
6	45	28	13
21	50	23	44
24	15	8	41

20	59	54	31
53	32	19	56
18	57	62	39
7	34	27	14

e. J-shape

2	55	8	45
35	30	57	38
10	47	50	53
17	34	31	58

13	46	1	54
64	37	4	61
49	62	9	44
36	25	16	33

42	29	56	39
3	60	7	52
18	43	48	59
11	32	51	24

19	14	41	28
12	27	22	5
63	20	15	40
26	23	6	21

f. J-shape

1	28	43	18
4	17	2	27
9	50	15	64
16	25	36	49

54	51	38	29
57	26	47	32
52	63	56	19
5	48	11	24

39	44	55	22
34	3	42	13
59	8	37	30
10	35	14	7

58	21	46	31
53	62	33	20
40	45	60	23
61	6	41	12

g. L-shape

20	33	58	7
17	60	31	48
32	63	6	43
5	44	61	26

1	8	19	54
4	51	22	35
9	34	15	64
16	25	36	49

18	59	30	57
21	56	47	42
28	41	62	55
45	50	27	24

29	2	53	12
46	13	38	23
3	52	11	40
10	39	14	37

h. L-shape

1	10	13	56
4	15	64	11
9	22	49	14
16	25	36	21

8	55	2	59
17	60	35	46
42	53	58	51
5	44	41	26

3	62	57	12
38	45	28	63
19	50	23	48
24	37	20	33

18	7	30	47
29	54	39	34
6	61	52	31
43	32	27	40

i. L-shape

40	31	18	47
17	58	51	44
32	41	54	57
5	52	15	42

1	48	61	28
4	45	64	35
9	62	49	46
16	25	36	63

30	59	50	19
39	34	23	56
6	53	60	43
33	14	55	24

7	2	29	12
22	13	38	27
3	8	11	20
10	21	26	37

j. L-shape

1	16	9	26
36	25	4	23
17	64	35	10
34	49	24	5

32	27	54	11
53	50	61	6
46	57	8	51
37	52	43	20

39	2	29	22
62	15	42	3
33	30	63	58
18	59	48	13

28	31	40	55
41	60	7	12
38	45	56	21
47	14	19	44

k. T-shape

10	39	46	17
43	50	53	24
40	47	60	45
31	44	23	52

1	16	9	62
36	25	4	51
11	64	57	18
42	49	30	33

38	63	56	19
41	48	37	54
58	55	8	61
7	32	59	22

27	2	5	14
6	15	28	3
35	26	13	20
12	21	34	29

l. T-shape

1	10	35	4
34	25	64	37
21	36	9	24
16	33	22	49

60	3	28	39
15	42	61	48
2	57	40	51
43	50	7	56

11	26	59	52
20	63	8	5
31	46	23	38
14	17	32	45

30	53	12	27
13	18	29	62
54	41	58	47
19	44	55	6

m. X-shape

62	29	14	33
15	56	41	50
18	45	60	13
59	20	17	40

1	32	61	4
58	25	64	39
63	36	9	44
16	57	42	49

30	55	34	27
47	28	51	24
52	31	46	35
19	48	21	12

53	26	3	38
2	23	8	5
7	54	37	10
22	11	6	43

n. X-shape

Fig. 42. Monogram tours (knight tours delineating letter shapes) in 4x4x4 cube.

3. Figured tours in four dimensions: Manning [21] mentions that “The notion of geometries of n dimensions began to suggest itself to mathematicians about the middle of the 19th century. Cayley, Grassmann, Riemann, Clifford and some others introduced it into their mathematical investigations.” Awani Kumar [22] extended knight's tour in hyperspace and constructed magic tours in four and five dimensions. Before we go for figured tours in four dimensions it is important for the reader to visualize a 4D hypercube. If we move a unit square a unit distance orthogonal to its plane in 3D space and join the corresponding corners, we get a cube. Analogously, we can imagine moving this unit cube a unit distance in an 'orthogonal' direction in 4D space to produce the 4D equivalent of a 3D cube, which is known as a 'hypercube'. However we can only show this by means of a perspective drawing as shown in Figure 43.

Fig. 43. Visualisation of a hypercube.

This way, we can visualize a hypercube and be comfortable (and confident) with its 'look'. The hypercube has 16 corners (derived from 2 cubes), 32 edges (2 cubes and joining lines) and 24 square faces. Figure 44 shows all the possible knight's moves from an inner cell in a $4 \times 4 \times 4 \times 4$ hypercube. Once the readers can visualize the jumps of the knight in hyperspace, they can count the possible number of knight moves from the nine distinct cell positions (lettered A to I) in the six planes (xy, xz, xw, yz, yw, zw) determined by pairs of the four coordinates x, y, z, w , as shown in Figure 45. On a two-dimensional board, knight has a choice of minimum 2 cells (when it is in the corner) and maximum up to 8 cells to which it can move. Now, readers can see that in 4D, knight has a choice of minimum $6 \times 2 (= 12$ cells) and maximum up to $6 \times 8 (= 48$ cells) to which it can move. In general, knight has a choice of minimum $n(n-1)$ cells and maximum up to $4n(n-1)$ cells to which it can move in a n -dimensional hypercube.

Fig.44. Possible knight's move in $4 \times 4 \times 4 \times 4$ hypercube.

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I
xy=	2	3	2	4	3	2	4	3	4
xz=	2	3	3	3	4	3	4	4	4
yz=	2	2	3	3	3	3	4	3	4
xw=	2	3	2	3	3	3	3	4	4
yw=	2	2	2	3	2	3	3	3	4
zw=	2	2	3	2	3	4	3	4	4
Total	12	15	15	18	18	18	21	21	24

Fig.45. Possible number of knight's moves from various cells in a 4x4x4x4 hypercube.

After having a clear picture of the possible knight moves in hyperspace, we come to the tour of knight in it. Knight cannot move at all in a 2x2x2x2 cube and can neither move-in nor move-out from the central cell of a 3x3x3x3 cube. So, 4x4x4x4 is the smallest cube in which both closed and open tours are possible in 4-dimensions and the author plans to look for 'Figured tours' in it. Figure 46a and Figure 46b show knight tour with square numbers in the corner cells and in the central cells of 4x4x4x4 hypercube, respectively. There are eight 4D space diagonals in a 4x4x4x4 hypercube. Figure 47a and Figure 47b show knight tour with square numbers along the 4D diagonals. Figure 48a, Figure 48b and Figure 48c show knight tour with square numbers in square, diamond and Beverley quartes, respectively. Knight tour with square numbers as three-dimensional trapezoid (or trapezoidal prism) has been shown in Figure 34. Its extension as 4-dimensional parallelotope is in Figure 49. Figure 50 shows knight tour with square numbers in closed zebra {2,3} path in 4x4x4x4 hypercube. Figure 51 shows open knight tour with square numbers in zebra {2,3} path in 4x4x4x4 hypercube. Here, only one square number is in each layer. Readers are requested to look for closed tour. Figure 52 shows closed tour of knight with square numbers and cubic numbers at knight move from cell 1.

1	60	11	256	18	21	14	59	13	58	17	20	16	19	46	81
12	57	50	85	83	86	151	148	152	147	84	87	79	82	15	38
51	22	111	106	154	149	208	205	145	234	153	48	118	47	80	45
144	107	96	49	117	200	143	150	220	183	146	199	169	78	125	36
52	89	110	179	141	228	189	242	2	251	244	255	137	140	3	44
55	92	97	88	116	201	142	215	239	214	211	198	170	193	126	123
26	109	102	241	209	188	245	190	246	229	240	243	187	136	129	42
95	56	113	108	114	191	210	195	213	194	221	182	192	35	122	39
27	10	101	254	226	253	248	231	247	230	237	252	186	135	128	41
94	61	112	217	167	216	207	204	212	233	218	181	119	172	185	76
23	90	105	180	164	173	236	249	235	250	223	232	168	139	134	37
54	93	98	203	155	202	165	206	222	219	184	197	171	120	77	124
100	91	104	9	163	174	227	160	238	159	224	177	225	138	133	4
53	8	99	178	156	161	166	175	7	176	157	74	162	75	130	43
28	69	24	103	115	72	131	68	158	67	70	5	71	132	127	40
25	62	29	196	30	65	32	73	33	6	63	66	64	31	34	121

Fig.46a. Knight tour with square numbers in the corners of 4x4x4x4 hypercube.

51	6	53	42	44	75	2	7	3	8	43	46	76	45	74	11
54	41	84	95	77	80	145	82	48	83	96	79	97	78	123	68
29	52	147	152	146	151	176	181	177	182	47	150	166	133	130	73
40	85	94	149	227	180	213	230	208	231	178	183	179	184	69	18
88	155	158	153	187	192	251	218	244	219	188	191	165	138	129	72
39	114	93	120	242	217	214	253	211	232	255	216	136	99	126	19
26	89	154	159	175	250	1	64	256	9	210	239	139	174	137	10
55	92	119	238	212	237	144	121	25	100	215	254	98	135	122	65
5	50	203	190	202	247	196	169	49	4	201	220	186	173	168	67
30	91	198	221	197	236	81	16	36	225	222	235	167	134	131	12
37	86	157	194	228	193	204	249	209	246	195	200	172	185	124	17
28	115	148	199	205	224	229	234	226	233	206	223	207	132	127	70
38	87	156	117	141	170	163	248	164	245	142	189	171	102	125	20
27	116	113	160	162	241	252	63	243	34	161	240	140	105	128	71
56	23	118	111	107	110	143	22	24	101	112	109	103	108	21	66
31	90	57	60	58	61	32	15	35	14	59	62	106	33	104	13

Fig.46b. Closed knight tour with square numbers in the centre of 4x4x4x4 hypercube.

1	38	21	102	134	5	40	125	39	22	37	42	4	41	6	23
106	103	2	117	3	118	57	24	58	127	120	101	119	56	67	54
59	116	147	124	156	133	98	151	135	150	155	126	132	99	74	43
104	149	154	25	207	152	157	192	158	193	206	153	163	128	55	100

20	137	142	177	213	224	173	218	250	219	210	239	131	96	75	70
17	62	183	240	184	81	216	203	211	196	249	220	162	165	72	45
136	123	174	143	199	246	225	222	214	221	36	245	189	198	97	8
61	26	145	182	190	197	204	247	205	248	215	194	166	161	66	11

107	122	175	238	200	255	226	235	209	234	251	244	188	171	130	7
60	115	146	181	227	64	201	254	230	121	228	195	167	160	65	10
105	108	237	176	208	223	256	243	233	252	169	236	170	129	68	53
18	63	148	241	231	242	191	202	168	229	232	253	159	164	73	44

16	109	138	141	187	172	217	178	212	179	186	139	49	76	69	52
19	112	91	114	80	89	94	111	185	110	113	180	88	95	48	71
92	15	86	83	87	82	47	140	50	85	78	35	77	34	51	46
27	90	93	144	30	33	28	13	79	14	31	84	32	29	12	9

Fig.47a. Knight tour with square numbers along the 4D diagonals in 4x4x4x4 hypercube.

1	14	27	256	70	45	42	47	153	48	15	44	86	43	46	41
28	95	88	91	87	90	71	94	150	93	26	89	69	72	83	6
13	2	155	140	154	141	172	163	173	162	151	92	152	85	68	73
196	139	160	169	171	148	197	228	198	195	170	161	149	142	105	84

54	57	136	209	179	236	233	204	186	211	208	247	177	188	107	76
31	138	157	214	192	225	36	251	221	248	213	224	184	143	66	37
10	55	166	203	237	144	9	234	212	167	246	215	187	176	23	8
29	158	115	252	220	253	238	217	245	216	223	168	222	147	82	39

135	132	165	202	240	205	230	235	207	200	243	210	190	175	24	7
12	117	96	255	231	254	239	218	244	49	16	201	193	146	103	40
33	58	133	164	206	241	232	229	199	4	25	242	174	189	106	5
116	3	156	159	181	226	219	250	194	249	182	227	183	104	67	74

32	137	134	131	191	130	35	124	178	125	122	129	121	110	77	64
53	56	113	118	180	145	98	127	185	128	119	112	102	99	108	75
30	79	34	59	101	126	123	80	120	111	78	63	109	62	65	38
11	52	97	114	18	61	20	51	21	50	17	60	100	19	22	81

Fig.47b. Knight tour with square numbers along the 4D diagonals in 4x4x4x4 hypercube.

31	60	3	86	62	1	66	29	65	30	61	2	24	67	28	15
50	85	80	59	89	82	107	256	84	93	90	87	63	88	83	68
33	94	91	104	64	105	200	175	199	176	187	92	142	139	106	27
48	51	108	101	201	184	81	192	188	193	198	177	165	178	141	70
34	55	78	159	153	208	219	170	204	223	162	157	167	16	23	18
53	58	99	156	230	233	244	191	245	228	197	234	164	179	182	169
154	103	160	97	205	238	247	218	248	215	222	237	25	168	163	20
43	96	155	190	246	227	232	241	229	236	189	214	180	183	144	13
111	4	161	172	206	239	254	217	253	216	211	224	152	207	148	137
32	95	110	225	243	226	231	240	212	235	252	173	181	138	145	14
49	56	79	102	250	209	220	255	221	194	249	210	166	147	26	69
52	47	100	109	185	242	251	174	202	213	186	195	143	140	71	146
54	57	112	125	151	124	135	158	134	9	150	171	149	136	17	22
35	46	77	98	132	127	130	123	203	122	133	196	128	131	72	19
44	5	116	113	129	10	73	126	36	115	76	117	75	8	21	12
37	42	45	118	74	119	38	41	39	6	121	114	120	11	40	7

Fig.48a. Closed knight tour with square numbers in square quartes in 4x4x4x4 hypercube.

25	126	91	6	90	5	24	119	23	118	7	130	88	131	22	117
92	79	144	125	87	120	123	140	184	141	224	143	157	116	53	132
27	64	83	128	122	139	146	173	89	206	129	178	152	147	138	21
86	67	124	81	183	200	213	180	214	181	142	199	185	158	133	54
28	75	14	193	253	192	233	174	16	231	228	221	187	234	17	56
15	62	227	170	226	203	212	255	239	218	169	204	150	191	156	19
12	127	2	175	189	254	249	194	248	1	240	167	245	188	151	50
93	80	85	198	246	195	202	171	217	168	247	256	190	201	52	155
13	78	229	176	4	235	250	163	251	222	237	230	244	115	8	135
26	65	84	197	243	208	225	172	216	205	242	177	209	136	149	154
3	68	145	164	252	121	236	179	241	166	223	162	186	153	134	55
66	63	82	161	215	182	211	196	210	207	160	165	159	148	137	20
74	61	108	77	109	114	99	220	238	219	232	111	9	110	57	18
29	76	73	104	98	105	102	113	101	112	107	48	106	59	100	35
42	71	38	69	37	60	95	34	10	47	70	39	97	36	51	58
11	30	41	72	94	33	44	103	43	40	31	46	32	45	96	49

Fig.48b. Closed knight tour with square numbers in diamond quartes in 4x4x4x4 hypercube.

1	46	21	56	60	57	44	13	45	14	59	94	58	11	76	43
22	55	4	95	87	10	77	92	48	93	86	15	61	88	91	12
47	2	85	16	172	79	98	167	193	140	173	96	164	97	62	75
54	9	134	3	189	166	171	78	174	191	194	139	195	188	165	90
20	65	142	215	201	80	99	204	64	141	154	157	163	160	63	26
5	104	135	178	246	161	242	217	231	228	49	236	220	245	72	89
84	17	24	143	221	250	203	214	200	213	230	25	249	162	243	42
23	126	179	138	232	241	222	239	229	36	235	218	244	219	240	73
83	132	129	206	208	255	202	211	199	210	207	254	256	183	252	41
106	125	180	137	181	120	223	238	224	237	234	177	247	186	225	74
53	128	133	130	248	209	170	205	175	198	253	212	182	251	184	169
8	105	136	127	119	190	233	168	192	227	176	197	185	196	187	226
52	103	82	131	81	150	145	216	152	155	158	147	159	146	151	110
19	66	107	124	118	123	100	149	113	148	153	156	38	111	116	27
6	51	102	69	101	70	115	144	34	67	50	109	117	122	71	40
33	18	7	108	114	121	32	29	37	30	35	68	112	39	28	31

Fig.48c. Knight tour with square numbers in Beverley quartets in 4x4x4x4 hypercube.

1	32	29	144	22	39	2	33	31	84	23	38	4	21	34	81
30	85	24	41	153	42	165	172	164	37	154	83	43	82	3	20
27	40	89	94	210	171	252	175	253	174	163	200	170	135	80	35
86	25	256	103	215	152	209	202	208	201	212	173	211	36	169	52
28	97	88	95	191	194	221	176	198	181	162	195	179	184	131	18
87	66	149	102	150	183	248	203	207	204	227	182	192	139	44	51
12	93	96	145	193	190	239	220	240	199	254	205	185	132	57	76
67	104	187	148	186	217	214	235	213	206	249	188	216	189	138	45
11	92	143	106	230	223	242	219	245	232	229	224	130	133	178	61
68	105	166	147	247	218	237	234	228	167	246	155	5	136	79	46
91	146	255	142	238	233	222	243	231	244	241	160	134	77	60	19
26	69	90	73	151	236	251	158	250	159	168	141	137	140	53	78
100	107	98	225	129	120	177	62	180	197	128	161	121	114	59	196
65	126	101	74	124	111	118	157	127	156	125	226	112	117	48	17
10	99	108	63	119	116	123	110	122	109	56	75	115	58	113	50
13	64	9	70	8	71	54	15	55	14	7	72	6	49	16	47

Fig.49. Knight tour with square numbers as 4-dimensional parallelotope in 4x4x4x4 hypercube

1	32	57	38	34	93	148	11	31	10	33	14	92	13	30	49
56	39	54	15	53	140	35	178	182	143	52	37	51	94	91	12
41	58	149	256	186	179	154	147	155	218	181	214	180	103	50	95
18	141	138	177	139	146	187	36	144	213	142	217	207	188	145	102
42	59	80	175	81	194	241	220	156	219	204	9	205	104	157	98
19	78	203	162	252	221	230	199	229	254	251	202	158	97	106	27
2	163	174	79	247	242	193	240	232	215	246	255	105	108	99	8
77	122	135	16	192	239	250	201	253	228	231	198	100	191	90	107
151	164	173	196	248	243	234	237	233	236	245	172	184	109	48	29
40	55	150	165	185	238	249	226	210	227	168	197	111	190	89	96
43	60	137	176	152	235	244	223	183	224	209	216	206	87	110	225
136	17	76	123	75	222	153	166	208	167	212	169	189	112	101	88
44	195	130	119	129	160	115	64	4	171	84	131	159	86	127	114
3	118	133	124	82	63	128	161	117	132	125	170	126	113	26	7
20	45	120	61	73	68	83	200	46	85	116	65	5	24	47	28
121	62	21	134	70	23	74	67	211	66	71	22	72	69	6	25

Fig.50. Knight tour with square numbers in closed zebra {2,3} path in 4x4x4x4 hypercube.

59	40	71	44	46	93	128	57	15	58	45	144	92	47	78	83
14	43	74	145	73	76	131	126	130	125	72	75	77	80	91	56
41	60	95	138	94	127	166	191	235	140	129	124	216	123	82	79
10	99	132	169	165	168	247	256	246	231	164	139	81	244	167	90
70	17	102	137	1	214	183	190	236	209	16	175	215	2	189	88
11	98	171	174	238	203	254	223	253	230	233	178	228	243	158	53
38	103	136	177	227	208	241	202	240	201	176	173	237	188	3	84
13	170	9	172	248	255	222	207	229	204	251	232	4	157	242	55
39	116	135	146	218	193	198	225	121	200	143	186	152	187	48	85
42	61	96	117	249	224	219	192	234	205	252	119	159	156	151	154
69	134	101	162	194	199	226	197	217	120	163	142	122	153	86	89
100	97	68	133	221	206	195	118	250	141	220	161	245	160	155	196
18	147	36	115	211	182	213	184	148	185	210	179	49	212	87	110
37	34	67	62	66	63	106	181	239	180	149	112	150	111	52	29
12	19	104	35	105	108	65	114	22	113	32	109	31	50	23	54
21	8	33	26	64	27	6	107	7	20	25	28	24	5	30	51

Fig.51. Open knight tour with square numbers in zebra {2,3} path in 4x4x4x4 hypercube.

1	6	55	52
54	51	16	5
15	4	53	56
50	57	80	73

136	133	128	7
139	126	137	134
196	135	14	127
125	138	195	176

187	8	17	132
216	213	186	177
211	246	193	214
194	215	212	185

18	89	92	9
91	86	19	88
188	13	90	25
173	182	87	20

70	67	100	131
49	62	69	72
36	71	66	61
65	60	83	202

101	204	159	248
124	199	236	203
255	252	221	232
84	237	228	251

256	247	206	233
235	238	229	200
220	231	234	249
227	250	219	230

205	198	151	24
172	181	160	21
197	164	93	12
190	85	170	161

35	144	129	78
64	59	82	75
3	76	79	130
58	63	74	81

2	253	222	241
223	240	225	244
140	243	254	209
191	224	175	184

145	242	143	208
226	245	218	239
217	210	207	178
174	183	192	201

142	165	94	27
189	168	171	10
166	141	26	163
169	162	167	22

48	77	68	99
39	42	47	44
34	45	38	41
37	40	43	46

123	98	153	158
102	115	122	113
107	112	147	116
104	31	114	111

154	119	150	179
121	180	155	118
146	117	120	109
33	110	105	30

149	152	157	96
156	97	148	23
103	108	95	28
106	29	32	11

Fig.52. Closed tour of knight with square numbers and cubic numbers at knight move from starting cell 1.

Figure 53 shows closed tour of knight with powers of 2 at knight move from starting cell 1. Figure 54 shows open knight tour with multiples of 12 at knight move from starting cell 1. Readers are requested to look for a closed tour. Figure 55 shows a closed tour of knight with multiples of 16 at knight move from starting cell 1.

1	70	37	74
40	73	4	69
71	2	75	38
76	39	72	3

190	217	16	65
129	68	221	212
216	211	66	239
67	238	231	220

193	64	189	214
10	233	192	63
61	252	215	210
234	201	62	253

188	17	26	15
191	202	11	18
194	187	60	25
203	232	19	176

80	95	6	43
5	42	87	78
8	79	44	89
41	88	77	86

205	228	197	240
196	241	236	219
227	218	229	198
230	199	222	237

256	251	244	209
235	208	223	254
206	255	226	243
9	242	207	200

195	186	59	24
204	163	174	177
179	172	185	14
184	175	178	173

83	36	81	48
32	47	84	131
45	82	7	140
136	85	46	133

128	181	246	213
167	130	127	134
182	125	166	169
165	168	135	126

245	124	225	250
224	249	138	123
121	170	247	132
248	137	122	139

180	171	152	27
183	160	21	12
158	151	58	153
161	164	159	20

96	49	112	141
91	94	33	52
50	35	90	93
31	92	51	34

113	146	101	56
100	53	98	147
97	102	55	142
54	99	30	103

120	155	106	111
107	110	119	116
114	117	108	105
109	104	115	118

157	150	57	154
162	145	148	23
149	156	143	28
144	29	22	13

Fig.53. Closed tour of knight with powers of 2 at knight move from starting cell 1.

57	40	63	16
64	15	138	103
39	4	233	164
14	65	136	183

98	3	56	41
13	102	59	96
94	97	100	127
101	60	95	124

93	42	17	62
58	61	92	125
99	126	165	246
236	195	232	199

18	55	52	43
91	2	19	54
122	119	82	51
149	90	123	20

186	167	142	163
11	34	185	168
32	141	166	193
9	36	33	140

143	162	227	192
202	1	242	177
213	254	207	228
12	243	204	239

212	225	218	245
237	244	221	216
220	217	234	255
203	238	215	194

159	24	83	88
144	89	48	21
151	84	145	176
214	47	150	45

67	106	187	130
8	129	104	139
105	66	137	128
38	5	184	135

210	189	208	229
173	248	205	240
206	209	190	253
201	252	241	182

219	230	223	188
222	197	250	247
235	256	231	198
196	249	200	251

174	161	146	23
147	120	53	44
160	175	118	87
121	148	81	50

154	131	68	107
31	6	169	134
10	35	76	69
7	30	37	74

157	108	191	70
72	171	156	181
155	132	71	178
172	73	170	29

224	111	226	179
153	180	113	110
112	77	116	133
115	28	75	78

211	158	25	86
114	109	80	49
117	26	85	22
152	79	46	27

Fig.54. Tour of knight with multiples of 12 at knight move from starting cell 1.

45	30	47	64
62	1	82	33
31	46	63	48
16	83	32	81

60	65	58	113
17	114	61	96
146	179	162	195
163	80	201	178

145	112	129	34
128	199	160	111
161	144	127	130
200	177	164	197

18	59	66	57
115	110	19	24
180	99	70	35
147	116	73	4

86	139	132	211
133	84	155	192
44	49	138	245
137	176	203	106

171	252	229	140
154	97	248	251
253	246	219	206
202	205	184	247

232	143	126	131
235	2	165	158
220	233	244	107
185	198	159	204

149	98	69	36
166	117	74	3
153	108	67	118
182	119	20	25

29	208	87	226
224	135	256	209
15	240	225	194
134	105	136	213

228	239	218	207
255	8	215	238
216	173	254	95
183	94	79	196

189	242	227	210
186	223	236	191
241	190	187	174
222	175	214	237

152	109	56	23
181	120	71	10
148	9	122	5
121	100	75	72

88	85	156	193
43	50	89	212
28	53	14	39
13	40	51	104

217	172	141	230
170	249	78	91
77	92	169	54
42	7	90	93

142	231	188	157
221	234	125	250
168	243	52	103
27	12	41	38

167	150	123	102
124	101	68	37
151	6	55	22
76	21	26	11

Fig.55. Closed tour of knight with multiples of 16 at knight move from starting cell 1.

'Domination by queen', as shown Figure 41, can be further extended in higher dimensions. Figure 56 shows possible queen's move in four dimensions and Figure 57 shows queen at cell 7 dominating all the primes in 4x4x4x4 hypercube.

Fig.56. Possible queen's move in 4x4x4x4 hypercube (shown as dots).

89	152	199	14	198	131	48	105	217	104	227	66	32	85	120	49
114	13	150	153	31	214	113	24	44	193	118	15	119	52	45	192
151	90	59	106	216	197	200	91	231	182	73	154	196	215	50	121
12	115	74	25	123	30	213	116	194	117	26	183	51	122	195	16
68	187	166	65	167	64	3	92	128	67	218	155	111	130	93	190
139	206	233	144	234	7	252	191	251	156	173	54	244	239	112	83
168	107	138	175	137	2	211	4	56	103	232	219	129	110	1	94
57	176	169	204	212	5	236	17	235	108	55	174	240	29	242	109
101	88	41	186	132	47	228	87	43	86	127	40	126	189	46	95
164	149	170	207	229	224	23	180	256	53	226	145	33	84	255	202
11	102	163	60	124	181	254	201	71	162	61	184	230	125	72	209
140	205	58	143	237	28	75	208	34	225	22	203	243	238	27	18
42	69	100	39	63	188	253	98	250	161	62	221	159	96	247	82
171	8	165	142	158	179	172	223	35	222	249	38	248	157	36	97
70	177	10	185	133	6	99	210	136	147	246	81	245	160	135	220
9	148	141	80	76	79	134	19	21	178	77	146	78	241	20	37

Fig.57. Queen (at cell 7) dominating all the primes in 4x4x4x4 hypercube.

Conclusion: Construction of figured tours is a mathematical recreation. It combines the logic of mathematics with the beauty of art. While compiling exhilarating figured tours, Jelliss [8] exhorts “There are many other possibilities yet to be investigated.” The author has shown few of them and readers are requested to look for more and improve upon the configurations as mentioned earlier. Jelliss [23] laments, “Despite ... efforts to raise further interest in this [Figured Tour] subject I seem to have been the only composer active in this field recently”. Well, you are no more alone Jelliss; we are with you. Kaku [24] asserts that “There is a growing acknowledgment among physicists worldwide, including several Nobel laureates, that the universe may actually exist in higher-dimensional space.” Pickover [25] declares “Various modern theories of “hyperspace” suggest that dimensions exist beyond the commonly accepted dimensions of space and time. The entire universe may actually exist in a higher-dimensional space. This idea is not science fiction ...” Musser [26] muses that “As fantastic as extra dimensions of space sound, they might really exist... various mysteries of the world around us give the impression that the known universe is but the shadow of a higher-dimensional reality.” Watkins [27] exclaims “... there is no reason to stop with chessboards in only three dimensions!” Accordingly, the author has shown possibility of figured tours of knight in higher dimensions and hopes that its study will help in unraveling secrets of hyperspace. It can also be used in pedagogy of higher mathematics, namely, differential geometry and topology.

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